

The Cruise Control Guide: a social-ecological framework to navigate the impacts of cruise tourism on nature and local communities

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Conference abstract presented at the *2024 Marine Socio-Ecological Systems Symposium* (MSEAS 2024), June 3–7, 2024, Yokohama, Japan.

Session: *“Running the Gamut Gauntlet: Socio-Ecological Modelling in a Complex World.”*

Cruise tourism has emerged in the last years as the fastest-growing segment in coastal and ocean-based tourism, attracting tens of millions of passengers each year to explore more remote destinations than ever before. However, as the cruise sector expands, there is a growing need to transition towards more sustainable tourism models. To tackle this challenge, cruise lines must account for their far-reaching impacts on the environment, societies, economies, and cultures of their destinations. Addressing these impacts requires holistic frameworks and interdisciplinary indicators that can provide information for adaptive management, facilitating sustainable decision-making. In this study, we developed and applied an innovative approach that combines social-ecological systems (SES) modeling with the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) framework. This methodology aims to identify the impacts on nature and local communities resulting from the interactions among the cruise sector actors. Our study revealed several direct and indirect impacts on natural capital and the well-being of local communities, spanning from habitat pollution and biodiversity loss to risks of social and economic inequalities as well as cultural heritage erosion. For each impact, we developed indicators and suggested responses to avoid or mitigate them. Indicators and responses were integrated into a single assessment and monitoring framework, named the "Cruise Control Guide." This framework serves as a valuable adaptive management tool for cruise lines, enabling them to assess the sustainability of their operations and informing the development of more sustainable cruise tourism practices.